

A SOLVENT-FREE COMPOSITE SOLID ELECTROLYTES OF $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ SYSTEM PREPARED VIA WATER BASED SOL GEL METHOD

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Abstract

Composite solid electrolytes in the system $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ were produced via a water based sol-gel process. The yielded gels were subsequently heated at 80 °C and crushed in an agate mortar. The composites were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The ionic conductivity was also carried out by impedance spectroscopy. Ionic conductivity studies showed that amorphous phase of Li_2CO_3 and intermediate crystalline phase formed at the interface of both Li_2CO_3 and alumina influence the ionic transport in the composite solid electrolytes. The maximum values of $\sim 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ were obtained at 130-180 °C for composite samples having composition $x = 0.4-0.5$.

1 Introduction

Composites are usually obtained by doping ionic conductors with insulating oxides such as ZrO_2 , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , TiO_2 etc. [1-4]. This heterogeneous doping has been widely used to improve physical properties and conductivity of the ionic conductors. Metal carbonates are one of the groups of compounds that are widely used in various fields [5] and have also been used as solid electrolytes [6]. Among the alkali and alkaline-earth carbonates, only lithium carbonate, Li_2CO_3 shows a fairly good conductivity and good stability against the humidity in the air [6]. However, poor ionic conductivity at low temperature is obtained when Li_2CO_3 salt is used as a composite material where alumina, Al_2O_3 is employed as dispersoid. The conductivity of $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite was found to be in the order of $10^{-8} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 250 °C [7]. The aim of this study was to improve the ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite solid electrolyte. In this work, $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite samples were synthesized via a simple sol-gel process without the use of organic solvent. Instead, deionised water was used as the solvent. The compositional and

temperature dependence of ionic conductivity were studied. The structural and thermal properties of the composites were also studied in order to understand their conductivities behavior.

2 Experimental

Powder compositions of the sample prepared are described by the general formula of $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ with $x = 0.0 - 0.7$ (mol percentage). Li_2CO_3 (high purity grade) and Al_2O_3 (high purity grade) powders were employed as starting materials with deionised water as solvent. In this sol-gel method, Li_2CO_3 was dissolved in water at room temperature. Subsequently, Al_2O_3 was added to this solution at constant stirring. After 45 minutes, the solution was slowly added to citric acid powder. The solution was then continuously stirred for 20 minutes at 60 °C and left to stand at room temperature for four weeks. The solution was then dried at 80 °C in an oven until it yielded a powder. The powder was ground in an agate mortar until a fine powder of the composite was obtained.

Structural characterizations of the composite were performed using a D8 Advanced-Bruker X-ray Diffractometer with Cu $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation for XRD and Perkin Elmer RX1 spectrometer for FTIR. The morphology was analyzed by SEM using INCA Energy 200 (Oxford Ins.). The thermal properties were measured on a Mettler Toledo DSC 822 with continuous heating at a rate of 10 °C min^{-1} . The conductivity measurements were carried out by impedance spectroscopy technique on a Solatron 1260 impedance analyzer. An AC amplitude of 100 mV in the frequency range $10^{-1} - 10^7$ Hz was used.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 SEM

The microstructures of the $(1-x) \text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composites ($x = 0.0, 0.3, 0.4$ and 0.6) studied by using SEM are shown in Fig. 1. Surface morphology of the pure ionic salt of Li_2CO_3 , $x = 0.0$ appeared to be agglomerated with crystalline features. However,

the alumina particles were homogeneously dispersed in the composite mixture of $x = 0.3$ and 0.6 . These types of distribution strongly indicate interfacial contact between the Al_2O_3 grains and the Li_2CO_3 phase. Fig. 1(b) shows the surface of composite sample with $x = 0.3$ with the ionic salt of Li_2CO_3 dominating the surface. Large grains of alumina seemed to dominate the whole surface when x increases. The change can be clearly seen in the micrograph of the sample with $x = 0.6$ (Fig. 1(c)).

The microstructure in Fig. 2(a) show that the composite with $x = 0.3$ consists of alumina particles (white) which are littered in an amorphous phase of Li_2CO_3 (dark area). A small amount of intermediate crystalline phase was also observed in the composite due to chemical reaction between both the Li_2CO_3 and Al_2O_3 crystalline phases. The amorphous feature of Li_2CO_3 can be seen in the composite sample with $x = 0.6$ as shown in Fig. 2(b). This sample is dominated by the alumina phase as depicted in Fig. 1 (c).

3.2 XRD

Fig. 2 shows the XRD patterns of the prepared $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composites. All the composite samples ($x = 0.1-0.6$) consisted of a mixture of crystalline Li_2CO_3 , Al_2O_3 and an amorphous phase. The peaks at $2\theta \approx 21^\circ, 23.8^\circ, 29.7^\circ, 30.5^\circ, 31.6^\circ, 34^\circ, 36^\circ, 37^\circ, 39.6^\circ, 42.7^\circ$ and 48.5° in the spectra are attributed to crystalline Li_2CO_3 .

The intensities of Li_2CO_3 peaks were observed to decrease when x increases. The XRD spectra revealed that the peak intensities of Li_2CO_3 especially at $\sim 23.8^\circ, 29.7^\circ, 36 - 39.6^\circ$ in the composite samples were too low compared to those of the pure Li_2CO_3 ($x = 0.0$). This indicated that a great amount of Li_2CO_3 had undergone a chemical interaction with alumina in the samples. Some peaks of Li_2CO_3 at $2\theta \sim 42.7^\circ$ and 48.5° disappeared with increasing x indicating that a high concentration of the amorphous phase was formed. This phenomenon is indicated by some peak broadening of the remaining Li_2CO_3 in the 2θ regions of $\sim 29-30.5^\circ$ and $\sim 36-37^\circ$.

A small amount of crystal phases of $\alpha\text{-LiAlO}_2$, $\gamma\text{-LiAlO}_2$ and LiAl_5O_8 were also detected in the composite samples with $x = 0.1 - 0.4$ as indicated by additional reflections at $2\theta \sim 10^\circ, \sim 15-29^\circ$ and $\sim 33^\circ$. This is due to the crystallization of this phase as a result of chemical reactions between the composite

components. However, the diffraction patterns suggested, the growth of crystal to be blocked by the presence of amorphous phase. There is no peak corresponding to these crystalline phases for the composite sample with $x = 0.6$ as shown in Fig. 2(b).

3.3 DSC

Fig. 4 shows DSC curves of the $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite samples. The temperature of glass transition was observed at $\sim 67^\circ\text{C}$ for $x = 0.1 - 0.6$. It showed that the composite samples prepared by this sol-gel method displayed glassy state at this temperature. For composite samples with $x = 0.1-0.3$, endothermic peaks of crystallization were observed at $\sim 110^\circ\text{C}$ (T_c) and $\sim 130^\circ\text{C}$ (T_c) which may correspond to incongruent melting of the intermediate phases discussed earlier. Similar behavior was also obtained for $x = 0.5$, but the crystallization temperatures were shifted to the lower values of $\sim 99^\circ\text{C}$ and $\sim 122^\circ\text{C}$ due to the high amorphicity of the composite sample.

The heat flow of the crystallization of samples at $\sim 110^\circ\text{C}$ decreased for $x = 0.1$ to $x = 0.3$. Much less heat at $\sim 99^\circ\text{C}$ was determined for the crystallization of sample $x = 0.5$. In contrast, the heat flow at $\sim 130^\circ\text{C}$ was observed to increase for $x = 0.1$ to $x = 0.3$. From table 1, we can see that much heat was absorbed for crystalline growth at $\sim 122^\circ\text{C}$ for the composite sample with $x = 0.5$ in order to overcome amorphous phase formed.

There is no phase transition observed in the DSC curve for sample with $x = 0.6$. The samples were found to be stable in the temperature range of $140 - 250^\circ\text{C}$. Table 1 shows the thermal properties of the $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite samples and their conductivities at higher temperatures. These will be discussed later.

3.4 FTIR

FTIR spectra obtained for $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite samples are shown in Fig. 5. The FTIR results confirmed that all samples with $x = 0.1 - 0.5$, have stretching and bending of Al – O bonds at $450 - 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [8]. Bands at this range are also attributed to stretching and bending of AlO_6 atomic group [8] which indicates the aluminum cations are residing in the octahedral sites in the alumina phase. The bands at $810, 700, 627, 550, 500$ and 450 cm^{-1} are associated with $\gamma\text{-LiAlO}_2$ and LiAl_5O_8 phases [9]. These confirmed their presence in the composite

samples with $x = 0.1 - 0.5$, as indicated by the XRD results discussed earlier.

3.5 Electrical Conductivity

Temperature dependence of conductivity for composite samples with $x = 0.1 - 0.7$ are presented in Fig. 6. The conductivities of the samples increased linearly with temperature in the range of 50 - 90 °C. The low temperature region represents the glassy state of the composites as indicated by the glass transition temperature in the DSC spectra. The glassy state slowly changed upon heating and thus the conductivities increased.

A sudden conductivity change occurred at ~ 110 °C and ~ 130 °C for composite samples with $x = 0.1 - 0.4$ due to intermediate crystalline phase present in the samples. The conductivities at these temperatures are dependent on the amount of the heat flow during the crystallization. From the list in Table 1, it is observed that the conductivity increases with decreasing heat flow of the crystallization for the composite samples with $x < 0.6$.

A conductivity plateau was observed beyond 140 °C in the Arrhenius plots of all samples. This is due to the presence of metastable amorphous phase formed on the $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ surfaces as a result of the interphase interaction. The composite samples with $x = 0.4 - 0.5$ showed the highest conductivity of $\sim 10^{-3}$ S cm^{-1} in this temperature region. This may be due to the presence of high concentration of metastable amorphous phase in the region.

In comparison with the literature on $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composites, the present system exhibit better conductivity value in the order of 10^{-3} S cm^{-1} (at ~ 140 °C) when $x < 0.6$ [7]. Thus, the sol-gel process employed in this work showed that it is a good processing technique for fabricating $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite solid electrolyte at moderate temperature.

Conclusions

The sol gel method has been developed for the fabrication of composite solid electrolytes in the system $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and does not involve the use of organic solvents. The composite prepared via this method is economical and enhances the ionic conductivity when $x < 0.6$. The present results show that interface phases of crystalline and amorphous exist in the composite samples. A maximum ionic conductivity of $\sim 10^{-3}$ S cm^{-1} was obtained at ~ 140 °C when $x = 0.4 - 0.5$.

Sample	$T_g/$ °C	$T_c/$ °C	Heat flow/ mJ s ⁻¹	$T_c/$ °C	Heat flow/ mJ s ⁻¹	$\sigma_{110}/$ S cm ⁻¹	$\sigma_{130}/$ S cm ⁻¹
$x = 0.1$	67	111	937	127	156	~ 4 $\times 10^{-4}$	~ 5 $\times 10^{-4}$
$x = 0.3$	67	109	347	128	621	~ 8 $\times 10^{-4}$	~ 4 $\times 10^{-6}$
$x = 0.5$	67	99	26	122	460	$\sim 10^{-6}$	$\sim 10^{-4}$
$x = 0.6$	69	-	-	-	-	$\sim 10^{-8}$	$\sim 10^{-8}$

Table 1: The thermal and conductivity data of $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite samples.

Fig. 1: SEM micrographs showing surface morphology of composite samples with (a) $x = 0.0$ (b) $x = 0.3$ and (c) $x = 0.6$.

Fig. 2: SEM micrographs of cross-section morphology of composite samples with (a) $x = 0.3$ and (b) $x = 0.6$.

Fig. 3: XRD patterns of $(1-x) \text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composites at (a) $x = 0.0$, (b) $x = 0.1$, (c) $x = 0.3$, (d) $x = 0.5$ and (e) $x = 0.6$ (curves 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 refer to Li_2CO_3 , Al_2O_3 , $\gamma\text{-LiAlO}_2$, $\alpha\text{-LiAlO}_2$ and LiAl_5O_8 , respectively).

Fig. 4: DSC curves for $(1-x) \text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite samples.

Fig. 5: FTIR for $(1-x)\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3-x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composite samples at $x = 0.1, 0.3, 0.4$ and 0.5 (curves 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively).

Fig. 6: The conductivities of $(1-x) \text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3 - x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composites as a function of composition and temperature.

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